

D1.8: Annual Report on Internal
and External Newsletter
produced during the second
year

WP1 Coordination

Responsible Partner: UoS

Contributing partners:

	<p>Other international stakeholder(s):.....</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>
--	---

Overview: One Health EJP Newsletters

The One Health EJP produces Consortium Newsletters (previously called Internal Newsletters) every quarter and External Newsletters twice a year. These newsletters are created by the Communications Team at the University of Surrey and the content is determined by the Communications Officer (CO), with input from consortium members. The CO contacts the Project Leaders, Work Package Leaders and Communication Contact Persons (CCPs) in advance to request input to the newsletters. The mailing lists for the newsletters are continuously updated in accordance to changes on the consortium membership spreadsheet (for Consortium Newsletters) or online subscriptions (External Newsletters). Each mailing list has approximately 350 subscribers. The Consortium Newsletter is opened by 25-30% of these subscribers and the External Newsletter is opened by approximately 40% of the subscribers.

The One Health EJP newsletters are created using MailChimp, which facilitates the creation of attractive documents and also allows the success of the newsletter to be monitored. MailChimp tracks the number of times each newsletter is opened, which links are clicked on and which link are most popular, and the number of people unsubscribing. This has also been set up to integrate with Google Analytics to monitor the traffic to the website from the newsletters.

Once the newsletters have been drafted, they are sent to the Project Management Team (PMT) for validation. PMT have one week to send feedback on each newsletter, after which the comments are addressed, and the newsletters are disseminated.

All newsletters are available on a dedicated [Newsletters page](#) on the One Health EJP website.

Consortium Newsletters

In 2019, the Consortium Newsletters were published in February, June and October by the CO.

The Consortium Newsletters target members of the One Health EJP consortium and are disseminated to PMT, Institute Representatives, Scientific Representatives, Programme Owner Representatives, Programme Managers Committee members, Project Leaders, CCPs, Stakeholders and active Third-Party members. Members are encouraged to further disseminate the newsletter within their institutes. For example, Project Leaders are encouraged to forward the newsletter to all members of their project consortia and the CCPs are encouraged to disseminate within their institute to anyone that may be involved or interested in the One Health EJP.

Although these newsletters are specifically targeted towards consortium members, they do not contain any confidential information and therefore can be widely disseminated. They are highlighted on the One Health EJP social media channels ([Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#)) and also posted on the [Newsletters page](#) on the website.

The Consortium Newsletters follow a similar template as follows:

- Highlights
- Events
- Key Announcement

- Updates from Work Packages
- Publications
- Social media links

This format can change depending on the content, however overall, this is the format adopted in the newsletters.

February 2019: <https://mailchi.mp/427607c3583d/ohejp-february-newsletter-review-313813>

The highlights section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The Work Package 6 funding calls to organise the Education and Training events for 2020.
- The One Health EJP Internal Events Survey, and the importance of completing this for dissemination activities.
- European Antibiotic Awareness Day.
- The launch of the new One Health EJP website.

The events section featured:

- A foodborne pathogens and whole genome sequencing workshop hosted by ANSES, France.
- The Scientific Steering Board Meeting, Bilthoven, the Netherlands.
- The Programme Managers Committee Meeting, ANSES, France.
- One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Dublin, Ireland.

The key announcement highlighted that registration was open for the first One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting. The Coordination structure change of the One Health EJP was also detailed. Project Leaders from IMPART, RaDAR, MedVetKlebs and COHESIVE provided project updates for this edition of the Consortium Newsletter. These updates detailed the key achievements or meetings within these projects and highlighted the success in the first year. As mentioned above, the WP6 funding opportunities were detailed in terms of key opportunities and dates. The final sections of this newsletter featured the most recent publications and highlighted the One Health EJP social media accounts.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (The number of recipients who opened this campaign any number of times: 76/287 (26.5%))

Total opens (The total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This count includes multiple opens from individual recipients): 1025

Number of links clicked: 13

June 2019: <https://mailchi.mp/275af5a3b0ea/ohejp-newsletter-to-june2019>

The highlights section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The success of the first One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting.
- The One Health EJP Summer School which took place in August 2019.
- The One Health EJP Internal Events Survey which all consortium members are encouraged to complete following a dissemination activity.
- The call for WP6 activities.

- The call for WP4 Integrative Missions.

The events section featured:

- The Programme Owners Committee (POC) meeting on the 19th June 2019 in France.
- The first One Health EJP Summer School on the 19th-30th August 2019.
- The SSB meeting on the 19th September 2019 in Madrid.

The key announcement highlighted the success of the first One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) in Dublin. Additionally, this newsletter provided Joint Research and Joint Integrative project updates from Project Leaders who agreed to provide the Communications Team with an update (AIR SAMPLE and COHESIVE). The Work Package 4 call for Integrative Missions was also highlighted in this newsletter to encourage further collaboration throughout the consortium. The success of the Work Package 6 (WP6) ASM Satellite Workshop was featured, the 2019 theme was Digital Innovation and Data Management which was jointly organised by SVA, Sciensano and the University of Surrey. Furthermore, the flyer for the One Health EJP Summer School also appeared in this edition. Other WP6 activities were celebrated, including the funding of 17 PhD studentships through the doctoral programme and the funding of 4 Short Term Missions in 2019. The launch of the funding opportunities for the WP6 2020 activities were also included with a graphic to detail all of the important dates for these calls.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens: 84/327 (25.7%)

Total opens : 376

Number of links clicked: 24

October 2019: <https://mailchi.mp/7edf0283e730/ohejp-october-consortium-newsletter2019>

The highlights section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The success of the One Health EJP Summer School 2019
- The funding of 13 more Joint Research Projects and 3 more Joint Integrative Projects following the September SSB meeting.
- The Internal Events Survey.
- The availability of the ASM presentations and documentation on the One Health EJP website, in addition to a new page to showcase the ASM on the front end of the website.
- The funding of 17 PhD projects through the One Health EJP doctoral programme.

The events section featured:

- The One Health EJP Nextflow Workshop on the 10th-11th October 2019 in Norway.
- The Netherlands Centre for One Health: Science Café on the 29th October 2019 in the Netherlands.
- One Health Day on the 3rd November 2019.
- The One Health EJP Stakeholders' meeting on the 12th November in Berlin.
- The One Health EJP Joint Research and Joint Integrative Project Kick-off meeting on 13th November in Berlin.
- The 6th World One Health Congress on the 14th-18th June 2020 in Edinburgh.

Following the events section, there was a reminder to Consortium members that more upcoming events are available on the One Health EJP website and that the Communications Officer can help with event promotion. Additionally, the new Communications Mailbox was advertised as a way for the Communications Team to more closely monitor events throughout the Consortium.

The key announcement of this edition of the Consortium Newsletter highlighted a more detailed account of the One Health EJP Summer School and its success in August. The publication of two important documents was also highlighted, the One Health EJP Strategic Research Agenda and the One Health EJP Annual Report. Consortium members were encouraged to read and share these documents, they were also made available on the One Health EJP website. A key event for this newsletter was the selection of the 13 new Joint Research Projects and 3 new Joint Integrative Projects at the September SSB meeting.

The successful applicants for the WP6 Education and Training activities were announced. The One Health EJP Communication and Media Workshop will be hosted by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, the Summer School 2020 will be hosted by Wageningen Bioveterinary Research Institute in the Netherlands and the first CPD module will be hosted by RIVM in the Netherlands in 2020.

Towards the end of the newsletter recent publications were detailed, in addition to a 'You may also be interested in...' section which was created to make Consortium members aware of other interesting topics. This edition highlighted that the One Health EJP had become part of the International One Health Coalition with the One Health Platform and that a new Education and Training Bulletin was now available for all members.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens: 102/348 (30%)

Total opens: 440

Number of links clicked: 55

Overall Consortium Newsletter Statistics:

Overall, the number of Consortium Members opening the newsletters is increasing with each edition. The average number of opens for a newsletter should be between 15-25% (source: MailChimp), we are exceeding this and suggesting that our newsletters are a success. The total number of opens between the February and June newsletters decreased by more than half, however this may be due to the February newsletter being the first of its kind sent by MailChimp to the Consortium and therefore was of increased interest to the recipients. In October, the number of opens improved, in addition to the percentage of opens and links clicked. This may have been as a result of the June newsletter being sent in the summer where recipients may be out of office and institutes and universities may be quieter. The statistics for all future Consortium Newsletters will continue to be monitored, with the hope to improve the rate of opening. It is important to monitor the statistics of these newsletters to ensure that the content is appropriate of the Consortium Members, and also to understand what percentage of members are receiving the information.

External Newsletters

In 2019, the One Health EJP External Newsletters were published in July and December.

These External Newsletters are targeted towards a wider audience compared to that of the Consortium Newsletter. The key audiences of the External Newsletter include:

- The general public
- Scientists external to the One Health EJP Consortium
- Stakeholders
- Individuals who have joined the external mailing list on the One Health EJP website.

Anyone visiting the One Health EJP website can subscribe to the External Newsletter mailing list which is used when disseminating this newsletter. Currently there are 366 subscribers to this newsletter (as of 27.01.20). Additionally, this newsletter is also disseminated to the internal mailing list including, PMT, Institute Representatives, Scientific Representative, Programme Owner Representatives, Project leaders, CCPs, approved Stakeholders, active Third-Party members and Programme Managers Committee.

The design and content of the External Newsletter is carefully considered to ensure that it is suitable, and attractive to a wide audience. The language is simpler to that of the Consortium Newsletter and does not contain complex science. There are links to relevant web pages if people wish to read and engage more.

July 2019: <https://mailchi.mp/4d7c92c70a55/one-health-ejp-external-newsletter-july>

The introduction of the One Health EJP External Newsletters was designed to provide subscribers with more information about the One Health EJP, this information is readily available on the website, however these newsletters can be used as a platform to highlight key information or information that subscribers may not know about the One Health EJP. This newsletter contained the One Health EJP brief which was designed at the start of the programme, this document succinctly summarises some of the key information about the One Health EJP. Following this, the Joint Research and Joint Integrative Projects were highlighted to ensure that those external to the consortium can understand what our Joint Research Projects and Joint Integrative Projects are. This was also important because the second round of projects would be announced in September.

The key highlight of this newsletter was the One Health EJP ASM, promoting this to external audiences was important to showcase our work and also to increase interest in our activities. The Programme Owners Committee and Programme Managers Committee meetings were also briefly reported on in this newsletter.

The success of the WP6 activities also featured, in particular the Doctoral Programme and the Short Term Missions, additionally links to the website were provided so that subscribers could read more about these successes. Upcoming events such as the One Health EJP Summer School were highlighted, in this edition we reported that there were over 130 applications for 20 places. A short message to let our subscribers know that the Scientific Steering Board would meet in September to discuss funding of the second round of Joint Research Projects and Joint Integrative Projects.

The External Newsletter also contains a 'You may also be interested in...' section, this edition features the 6th World One Health Congress in June 2020 and the One Health EJP Education and Training Bulletin.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

External Mailing List:	Internal Mailing List:
Number of opens: 98/263 (41%)	Number of opens: 92/327 (28.1%)
Total opens: 263	Total opens: 308
Number of links clicked: 68	Number of links clicked: 20

December 2019: https://mailchi.mp/7207a8d08357/ohejp-external-newsletter_dec19-553173

This External Newsletter celebrated the success of the second year of the One Health EJP and highlighted that the second One Health EJP ASM is to be held on 27th-29th May 2020 in Prague. The ASM announcement thanks our partners the Veterinary Research Institute (VRI) and the National Institute of Public Health (SZU) in the Czech Republic, for organising the event, in addition to making subscribers aware of the new ASM website and directing them to the One Health EJP website to read about the success of the 2019 ASM. Furthermore, the ASM Satellite Workshop details were announced, with more information available on the website.

The JRPs and JIPs were once again highlighted in a ‘Did you know?’ section. This reminded subscribers that the One Health EJP currently funds 13 JRPs and JIPs and that when the second round of projects starts in January 2020, a total of 29 projects will be funded. Additionally, the Project Leaders from COHESIVE, MedVetKlebs and AIR SAMPLE volunteered to provide updates from their projects. This is an important section to showcase the ongoing research within the Consortium. Images from the SSB meeting in September, Stakeholders’ Meeting in November and the Project Kick-off Meeting also in November were added to this newsletter to show just how much collaboration is ongoing in the Consortium!

A celebration of the 2019 WP6 activities features in this newsletter. This included the Summer School, Doctoral Programme and Short Term Missions. This was also the first opportunity to disseminate the PhD project pages available on the website.

In the ‘You may be interested in..’ section the ORION One Health Glossary was advertised as this is a tool for all audiences. Additionally, the EU project EU-JAMRAI launched a competition to design a tangible symbol to raise awareness of Antimicrobial Resistance and would be interesting for our audiences. As a reminder, the One Health Congress and Education and Training Bulletin also featured in this newsletter. Finally, we wished everyone a very Merry Christmas and Happy New Year!

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

External Mailing List:	Internal Mailing List:
Number of opens: 134/334 (40.1%)	Number of opens: 103/397 (28.1%)
Total opens: 425	Total opens: 548
Number of links clicked: 151	Number of links clicked: 60

Overall External Newsletter Statistics:

Overall, the number of opens by our external audience is promising and indicates that our External Newsletter is created with the correct content for the audience. The number of subscribers to the External Newsletter increased by 71 between July and December, furthermore the total number of opens nearly double between the newsletters. Additionally, the number of links clicked more than doubled, showing that many of the subscribers are visiting the website for more information. The percentage of opens from the internal mailing list is as expected and in line with the percentage of opens for the Consortium Newsletter. At 28%, this is still above average for percentage of opens expected from a newsletter. The Communications Team would like to see more Consortium Members opening the newsletters because they contain important information for all members. There was a considerable increase in the total number of opens and the number of links clicked by the internal audience between the July and December newsletters, however as with the Consortium Newsletter this may be as a result of the July edition being sent in the summer when many people may be out of office. Additionally, there was also a Consortium Newsletter in June, therefore it may be necessary to send the newsletters at different times. This will be explored in year 3.

Future Newsletters

The future Consortium Newsletters will be disseminated in February, May, August and November 2020.

The future External Newsletters will be disseminated in June and December 2020.

There will also be 4 Consortium newsletters in Year 3 and Year 4, and an additionally 2 External Newsletters in Year 3 and Year 4.